

Partial molar volumes and their temperature derivatives for potassium nitrate, magnesium nitrate and calcium nitrate in binary aqueous solutions of urea

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The partial molar volumes of potassium nitrate, magnesium nitrate and calcium nitrate have been determined in binary aqueous solutions of urea at different mole fractions of urea and at different temperatures from the density measurements. The density data have been analysed using Masson's equation. The limiting apparent molar volumes (Φ_v^0) and the experimental slopes (S_v) have been interpreted in terms of ion-solvent and ion-ion interactions respectively. The Φ_v^0 values vary with temperature as a power series of temperature. The structure-making/breaking capacities of the electrolytes have been inferred from the sign of $[\partial^2 \Phi_v^0 / \partial T^2]_P$. All the electrolytes studied behave as structure-makers/promoters in the present system.

Urea and urea derivatives are frequently used as denaturing agents of polypeptides, proteins and other biopolymers. The increase in the solubilities of lighter hydrocarbons at room temperature in aqueous urea solutions¹ is often offered in the literature as a proof that urea weakens the hydrophobic interactions. The same conclusion was reached from the studies of thermodynamic and transport properties from water to aqueous urea solutions of solutes containing alkylic groups². As partial molar volume of a solute reflects the cumulative effects³ of ion-ion and ion-solvent interactions, it would be of interest to study partial molar volumes of some strong electrolytes in urea + water systems. Such data are expected to highlight the role of cations and of anions of an electrolyte in influencing its partial molar volumes at infinite dilution in mixed solvent systems. These considerations prompted us to undertake the present study.

Results and Discussion

The densities of potassium nitrate, magnesium nitrate and calcium nitrate in urea + water (at mole fractions of urea, $X_{\text{urea}} = 0.010, 0.025, 0.050, 0.075$ and 0.100) solutions, measured at 308 K have been used to calculate the apparent molar volumes (Φ_v) of the solute. The plots of Φ_v against square-root of molar concentration ($C^{1/2}$) were found to be linear with negative slopes. The limiting apparent molar volumes (Φ_v^0) have been calculated using the least-squares fit to the plots of Φ_v vs $C^{1/2}$, using Masson's equation⁴,

$$\Phi_v = \Phi_v^0 + S_v C^{1/2} \quad (1)$$

where, $\Phi_v^0 = \bar{V}_2^0$ is the partial molar volume of the solute at infinite dilution. The values of Φ_v^0 and S_v along with standard errors are recorded in Table 1. It is evident from Table 1 that the values of S_v are negative for all the nitrates, stud-

Table 1. Partial molar volumes (Φ_v^0), experimental slopes (S_v) and partial molar volumes of transfer ($\Delta\Phi_{v, \text{tr}}^0$) for potassium nitrate, magnesium nitrate and calcium nitrate in urea + water solutions at 308 K*

Urea + Water mole fraction (X_{urea})	$\Phi_v^0 = \bar{V}_2^0$ cm ³ mol ⁻¹	S_v cm ³ dm ^{3/2} mol ^{-3/2}	$\Delta\Phi_{v, \text{tr}}^0$ cm ³ mol ⁻¹
Potassium nitrate			
0.000 (water)	24.55 (0.34)	36.50 (1.09)	—
0.010	47.08 (0.49)	-31.90 (1.67)	22.53
0.025	58.73 (0.28)	-46.81 (0.94)	34.18
0.075	70.88 (0.28)	-71.65 (0.93)	46.33
0.100	63.32 (0.69)	-53.44 (2.28)	38.77
Magnesium nitrate			
0.000 (water)	139.16 (0.09)	31.05 (0.33)	—
0.010	154.67 (0.10)	-12.32 (0.38)	15.51
0.025	159.91 (0.24)	-16.95 (0.87)	20.75
0.050	175.14 (1.33)	-56.29 (4.00)	35.98
0.075	178.43 (0.46)	-53.95 (1.64)	39.27
0.100	179.63 (0.94)	-52.64 (3.65)	40.47
Calcium nitrate			
0.000 (water)	128.36 (0.09)	-13.31 (0.35)	—
0.010	132.80 (0.21)	-19.47 (0.78)	4.44
0.025	138.12 (0.49)	-39.02 (1.79)	9.76
0.050	138.51 (0.15)	-35.72 (0.53)	10.15
0.075	139.62 (0.28)	-29.97 (1.01)	11.26

*Standard error is given in parenthesis.

ied here, in various mole fractions of urea at 308 K. The results indicate that all the nitrates mix ideally with urea + water and there is a perfect solvation of these molecules resulting into the absence of significant ion-ion/solute-solute interactions. Further, it is also clear from the results that S_v is positive for potassium nitrate and magnesium nitrate

in pure water and becomes negative just on the addition of very small amount of urea. These results suggest that potassium nitrate and magnesium nitrate do not mix ideally with water resulting into strong ion-ion interactions, but on the addition of only a small amount of urea the mixing becomes ideal meaning thereby that urea has more affinity for these nitrates as compared to water alone. In other words, the solvation of the ions improves on the addition of urea thereby resulting in the absence of significant ion-ion interactions.

The volumes of transfer were calculated (Table 1) using equation (2),

$$\Delta\Phi_{v, \text{tr}}^0 = \Phi_v^0(\text{MS}) - \Phi_v^0(\text{W}) \quad (2)$$

where, $\Phi_v^0(\text{MS})$ and $\Phi_v^0(\text{W})$ are the limiting apparent molar volumes of an electrolyte at infinite dilution in mixed solvent and in pure water respectively. The values of $\Delta\Phi_{v, \text{tr}}^0$ are positive for all the three nitrates in different mole fractions of urea + water solutions and which increase in magnitude with the increase in mole fraction of urea at 308 K. Since NO_3^- is the common ion in all the three electrolytes, therefore, from the values of $\Delta\Phi_{v, \text{tr}}^0$ at a particular mole fraction of urea, which vary in magnitude in the order : $\text{K}^+ > \text{Mg}^{2+} > \text{Ca}^{2+}$, it may be expected that the extent of electrostriction for these cations follows the order : $\text{Ca}^{2+} > \text{Mg}^{2+} > \text{K}^+$. Thus, it may be inferred that the observed order is due to the preferential solvation of cations by urea and the order of strength of preferential solvation of these cations is : $\text{K}^+ > \text{Mg}^{2+} > \text{Ca}^{2+}$. Further, as the value of $\Delta\Phi_{v, \text{tr}}^0$ increases with the increase in mole fraction of urea in water, the extent of preferential solvation for a particular cation increases with the increase in urea content in the mixed solvents, thereby reducing the strong⁵ solvent-solvent interactions between urea and water.

Effect of temperature : Since the behaviour of individual nitrate was found to be qualitatively similar in solvent with the different mole fractions of urea in water at 308 K, only the solvent with $X_{\text{urea}} = 0.025$ was selected for studying the effect of temperature. The sample plots of Φ_v vs $C^{1/2}$ for magnesium nitrate at 303, 308, 313 and 318 K are linear. The values of limiting apparent molar volumes (Φ_v^0) and the experimental slopes (S_v) obtained by using least-squares fit to the above plots are given in Table 2.

The values of S_v for all the three nitrates at all temperatures are negative. The value of $\Delta\Phi_v^0$ decreases with the rise in temperature for potassium nitrate and magnesium nitrate, whereas it increases slightly even with the large increase in temperature for calcium nitrate.

The temperature dependence of Φ_v^0 in the solvent with

Table 2. Partial molar volumes (Φ_v^0 , $\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$), experimental slopes (S_v , $\text{cm}^3 \text{dm}^{3/2} \text{mol}^{-3/2}$) and partial molar expansibilities (Φ_E^0 , $\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$) for potassium nitrate, magnesium nitrate and calcium nitrate in $X_{\text{urea}} = 0.025$ urea + water at different temperatures*

Parameter	303 K	308 K	313 K	318 K
Potassium nitrate				
Φ_v^0	64.37 (0.46)	58.73 (0.28)	50.76 (0.23)	48.59 (0.34)
S_v	-61.66 (1.54)	-46.81 (0.94)	-22.43 (0.77)	-18.11 (1.13)
Φ_E^0	-1.627	-1.280	-0.933	-0.586
Magnesium nitrate				
Φ_v^0	165.57 (0.17)	159.91 (0.24)	157.12 (0.11)	155.65 (0.15)
S_v	-30.54 (0.64)	-16.95 (0.87)	-5.99 (0.41)	-6.51 (0.54)
Φ_E^0	-1.280	-0.861	-0.442	-0.023
Calcium nitrate				
Φ_v^0	137.82 (0.31)	138.12 (0.49)	138.86 (0.12)	140.73 (0.39)
S_v	-41.23 (1.12)	-39.02 (1.79)	-37.48 (0.44)	-48.39 (1.43)
Φ_E^0	-0.046	0.111	0.268	0.425

*Standard error is given in parenthesis.

$X_{\text{urea}} = 0.025$ for potassium nitrate, magnesium nitrate and calcium nitrate can be expressed by the equations,

$$\Phi_v^0 = 3743.4 - 22.655 T + 0.0347 T^2 \quad (3)$$

for potassium nitrate,

$$\Phi_v^0 = 4400.0 - 26.671 T + 0.0419 T^2 \quad (4)$$

for magnesium nitrate, and

$$\Phi_v^0 = 1593.2 - 5.560 T + 0.0157 T^2 \quad (5)$$

for calcium nitrate.

The temperature T is expressed in Kelvin.

The partial molar volume expansibilities, $\Phi_E^0 = [\partial\Phi_v^0/\partial T]$ calculated from equations (3) to (5) for potassium nitrate, magnesium nitrate and calcium nitrate respectively, are also recorded in Table 2. It is clear from the results that the value of Φ_E^0 increases in magnitude with the increase in temperature, thereby indicating that the behaviour of all the three nitrates is just like the symmetrical tetra-alkyl ammonium salts⁶ in binary aqueous solutions of urea and unlike that of common salts^{7,8}, because in common salts the molar expansibility should decrease with the increase in temperature. The positive increase in Φ_E^0 with the increase in temperature for all the three nitrates may be ascribed to the 'caging effect'^{6,8}.

During recent years it has been emphasised by various workers that S_v is not the sole criterion for determining the structure-making or -breaking nature of any solute. Hepler⁹ developed a technique of examining the sign of $[\partial^2\Phi_v^0/\partial T^2]_p$ for various solutes in terms of long range structure-making

or -breaking capacity of the solutes in aqueous solutions using the general thermodynamic expression,

$$[\partial \bar{C}_p / \partial P]_T = - [\partial^2 \Phi_v^0 / \partial T^2]_P \quad (6)$$

On the basis of this expression it has been deduced that structure-making solute should have positive value, whereas structure-breaking solute negative value. In the present system it is observed from equations (3) to (5) that $[\partial^2 \Phi_v^0 / \partial T^2]_P$ is positive for potassium nitrate, magnesium nitrate and calcium nitrate in urea + water ($X_{\text{urea}} = 0.025$) solutions, which means that all the nitrates behave as structure-makers/promoters in binary aqueous solutions of urea.

Experimental

Potassium nitrate, magnesium nitrate, calcium nitrate and urea (A.R., Sd fine Chemicals) were used as such, only after drying over P_2O_5 in a desiccator for more than 48 h. Freshly distilled conductivity water (sp. cond. $10^{-6} \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$) was used. The binary aqueous solutions of urea of varying mole-fractions as well as the solutions of nitrates were made by weight, and conversion of molality into molarity was done¹⁰.

The density was measured with the help of an apparatus similar to the one described by Ward and Millero¹¹. The glass sample cell had a bakelite top with a hole in the centre and was placed in a water-bath ($\pm 0.1^\circ$). The glass-float weighed 37.8192 g and had a volume of 16.1760 cm^3 (± 0.0002) at 303 K. Density was calculated with the relation, $d = d_0 + (W_0 - W)/V_f$, where d and d_0 are the densities of sample solution and pure water respectively, W and W_0 the weights of float in the sample solution and pure water and V_f is the volume of the float. The accuracy of the system was checked by measuring the density of pure ethylene glycol at 303 K. Our value of $d = 1.0662 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$ is in good agreement with the literature value (1.0664 g cm^{-3})¹².

The apparent molar volume (Φ_v) was calculated from

the density data using the expression¹³,

$$\Phi_v = \frac{M_2}{d_0} - \frac{1000}{C} \left[\frac{d - d_0}{d_0} \right] \quad (7)$$

where C is the molar concentration of the solute, d the density of the electrolytic solution, d_0 the density of solvent (urea + water) and M_2 the molecular weight of the solute.

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